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Adult Education as a Tool For Effective National Security and Sustainable Economic Development In Nigeria

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Abstract

In recent years, Nigeria, like many other African countries have been battling with various degrees of civil unrest, ranging from communal clashes, ethno-religious intolerance occasioned with political violence. National security is described in this paper, as freedom from or resilience against potential harm caused by others. In all the violent conflicts, youth have been the willing tools in the hand of politicians or religious zealots in causing troubles in the land. The reason is premised on the high rate of unemployment and underemployment among the youths which is fallout of faulty educational system that renders Nigerian youth's unemployable in the labour market. The economic predicaments of the Nigerian youths have made them ruthless in crimes and unethical behaviours. It is an established fact that qualitative education can reduce incidences of insecurity and restiveness among the youths, if not totally eradicated. Education, this paper revealed is a major weapon of progressive social change. The paper therefore examined the relevance of adult education and various problems it faces in Nigeria which, if not solved, constitutes hindrance to successful sustainable security and economic development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Adult Education, Effective Security, Sustainable Economic Development

Introduction

Nigeria as a nation is presently grappling with gross underdevelopment, killings, kidnappings, murder, poverty, inequality, hunger, banditry and gross insecurity, violence, ethnic conflicts and religious crisis (Ogechi, 2021). There is also no gainsaying that Nigeria is currently facing serious security challenges, that have put every citizen on the edge including those at the helm of affairs and even the security operatives saddled with the responsibility of securing lives and properties. Hardly can citizens sleep with their two eyes closed as a result of constant attacks on various communities. In the last ten years, there have been a dramatic twist on the wave, dynamics and sophistication of insecurity in Nigeria (Ubong, et. al., 2019). Insecurity that used to be one of the lowest concerns in the hierarchy of Nigeria's social problems has now assumed an alarming proportion. A time we thought that corruption and power failure have the crown of our problems, insecurity in the country has now taken the centre stage (Seji, et. al., 2020). Boko Haram activities, Fulani Herdsmen invasion of communities, money ritualists, internet fraudsters ("yahoo boys"), fake prophets and other secret gangs have created undue hardship, confusion, loss of control, and lack of trust among citizens all gearing towards insecurity (Rabiu & Muhammad 2013).

Education generally plays a key role in overall human development and as well as the backbone of any country's sustainable national growth and development be it security or economic development. Education is usually associated in most countries of the world with formal learning, just the education of children and the young ones alone leaving out the adult members of the communities and cities, the vulnerable and all other marginalized groups. Whereas, United Nations declaration 2030, stated that the right to education is a human right that must be enjoyed by all, irrespective of age and where located (Ogechi 2021) Education should be for all as it is deemed a universal thing and that it must be inclusive, equitable, of good quality and one that promotes lifelong learning for all. The essence of education is further established that education is a public good, a fundamental human right and a basis for achieving, for guaranteeing the realization of other rights (United Nation

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2015). The above implies that for any type of development to be sustainable, secured and maintained, education must reach all, ignorance must be wiped out and illiteracy must be subsided. Adult education must therefore play a key role in the nation's socio-economic development to curtail the problems of insecurity.

Adult Education and sustainable economic Development in Nigeria

Adult education as an integral part of education plays a key role in sustainable development, promotes economic growth, as well as social, and environmental dimensions to sustainable development and creates favourable conditions for empowering citizens globally for development. Adult Education is a learning process whether formal, informal and non-formal which the adult engages in for skills acquisition, knowledge, better information equipment and development. Adult Education can generally be taken as any form of learning undertaken by men, women and youths in the formal or non-formal school system. The main targets of adult education are specifically (girls and boys over 15 years of age, the migrants, the normads, drop out, less privileged, physically challenged, professionals, workers and educationally disadvantage people in the society among others) (Ubong et al 2019). Although literacy continues to be emphasized, adult education also includes computation of figures, problem solving, acquisition of skills and numerous forms of knowledge impartation (Ogechi, 2021). Adult Education emphasizes all forms of functional education programmes for youths and adults outside the formal school system (Aderinoye 2007). Such education programmes include basic literacy programme, post literacy programme, continuing education programme, and vocational education programme (FRN Blue Print 2008). These adult education programmes are geared towards human and national development which encompasses security and economic development. Nzeneri (2010), quoting a UNESCO working document, sees adult education in a more encompassing way as the entire body of organized educational process, whatever the content, level and method, formal or otherwise, whether they prolong or replace initial education in schools, colleges and universities as well as apprenticeship, whereby persons regarded as adults by the society to which they belong develop their abilities, enrich their knowledge, improve their technical or professional qualifications and bring about changes in their attitude or behaviour in the two fold perspectives of full personal development and participation in balanced and independent social, economic and cultural development of the society. The above opinion is broad and encompassing in that, it does not only define adult education but it also defines its content and scope.

Adult education provides employers in different sectors of the economy with qualified and sustainable skills and manpower which service the economy and provide basis for rewarding the adult members (Okemakinde and Ogunyinka 2016). Farhey (2010) observes that: "people who are more educated know why they are not supposed to make prejudice comments and consequently disguise their prejudices". Adult education, by solving the problem of injustice, deprivation and oppression brings peace and harmony among adult members of the country and hence ensures sustainable security and economic growth and development. It will by no means solve the current problems of kidnapping, youth restiveness and insurgency in the country if properly annexed. Fasokun (2006) observes that: adult education is concerned not with preparing people for life, but rather with helping people (adults) to live more successfully as useful and acceptable members of their societies and contribute meaningfully to the overall development of those societies. Hence, the benefits of adult education to the overall development and the security challenges in any nation and to individuals cannot be over-emphasized by bringing peace and tranquility.

Adult Education and Effective National Security in Nigeria

The issue of security is not alien as it has been the central focus of primitive society. In the same vein, Audu et. al., (2014), argued that since the end of the cold war, there appears to be shift from viewing security from state-centric perspective to a broader view that places emphasis on individuals, in which national security also encapsulates human security, human right and national development. National security according to Iredia (2011), simply mean, the capacity of a state to overcome challenges confronting her. Iredia (2011) also opined that national security is not limited to military might, defense or law enforcement; it covers basic dimensions like job, water and food security. National security is also seen as a state or condition in which most cherished values of a country and the people are permanently protected and continuously enhanced. The concept of security also denotes the condition or feeling of safety from harm or danger. It also means the defense and protection of values acquired. Security has to do with freedom from danger or threat to a nation's ability to protect and develop itself, promote its cherished values, legitimate interests and enhance the well-being of its people. Internal security implies freedom from danger to life and prosperity. Audu, et al (2014), explained security as any mechanism devised to alleviate the most serious threats that prevent people from pursuing their cherished values. While, according to Mezieobi (2012) the term security brings to mind issues that pertain, predominantly, to one or a combination of the following whenever it is discussed:

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1. The defence and protection of national integrity or Nigeria's sovereignty, territorial and political jurisdictions from external and internal interferences or intervention;
2. Personal safety of members of political class who are in control of the helm of affairs of governance, in addition to safeguarding or protecting their office, hence the incredible allocation of funds for security services;
3. The security agents or forces, civil defence corps protecting the lives and properties of the mass of the defenseless citizenry against the menace of the men of the underworld;
4. Forestalling or deterring possible internal attacks or crises and subjugating insurgency;
5. Keeping the security agents on active security alert and readiness at all points in time;
6. Checkmating impending or actual internal threats to state or national security or anti-social behaviours by those who are deliberately undermining or sabotaging government efforts;
7. Checkmating social problems such as Boko-Haram saga and youth militancy, kidnapping/abduction that may pose threat to state and national security and detract the political cadre in control of state affairs from active commitment to their functions; and
8. By making the environment free from insecurity to attract international investment.

This is in line with Robert McNamara's earlier quoted assertion on the relationship between growth, national development and peace and security. From the above, security therefore can mean the state of being free from danger, risk or threat. It covers freedom from anxiety, fear, the safety of a state or organization against criminal activities and attacks like terrorism, theft or espionage (Ogheneakoke, 2014). The security interests of any nation therefore include safety of lives and properties, economic, physiological, mental well-being and the freedom to pursue the attainment of objectives without hindrance. Hence, insecurity implies a state of vulnerability to attacks, danger or threats to a people, their properties, cherished values and the inability of the nation to protect its citizenry. Alemika (2016) postulated that insecurity can be classified into several dimensions with the most significant dimensions as:

1. Physical insecurity- violent personal and property crimes;
2. Public insecurity- violent conflicts, insurgency and terrorism;
3. Economic insecurity- poverty, unemployment;
4. Social insecurity- illiteracy, ignorance, diseases or illness, malnutrition; water borne disease, discrimination and exclusion;
5. Human right violations- denial of fundamental rights by state and non-state actors in different states; and
6. Political insecurity- denial of good and social democratic governance

The dimensions of security as highlighted above are interwoven and cannot be treated in strict isolation as explicated by Anan (1998) cited in (Joshua, Dominic and Ibieta 2016) that: "Security" today means far more than absence of conflict knowing that lasting peace requires a broader vision encompassing areas such as education, health, democracy and human rights, protection against environmental degradation and the proliferation of deadly weapons. Also, there cannot be security amidst starvation, peace cannot be without alleviating poverty, and freedom cannot be built on the foundations of injustice. These pillars are understood as people-centered concept of human security which is interrelated and mutually reinforcing.

Condoleezza Rice, former Secretary of State of the United States of America posited that quality education of a nation is a direct function of a country's national security (Joshua, et al 2016). This relationship springs from the role education plays in providing the knowledge base for technological training, advancement and human capital development. Thus, education is as important as national security. The Boko Haram insurgency has become a festering sour because the Nigerian military are fighting 21st Century Islamic military insurgency with nineteenth Century military education (Ejirika, 2014). In the Nigerian context, internal security particularly from 2007 till date seems to be elusive (Joshua et al 2016). Some of the indicators of insecurity in Nigeria include; ethno-religious conflicts, violence, kidnapping, terrorism among others. Insecurity has taken different dimensions in the various regions in Nigeria. For instance, in the Niger Delta region (South-South), the militants slugged it out with oil companies in the area, killing and destroying oil company's properties as well as Federal Government properties especially from 1999-2007 (Joshua et al 2016) In Jos, Plateau State (North Central), the Hausa and the indigenes have been at war from around 2002 till date. In South-East, kidnapping, ritual killing, herdsmen -farmers clashes and armed robbery has been the nature of insecurity in the region same with the South-West region of the country.

Boko Haram insurgency has been the greatest challenge to internal security in the North-East, North-West and North Central from 2009 till date (Joshua et al 2016). Fear, apprehension and jitteriness have become the lot of Nigerians. Consequently, huge amount of fund is always allocated to security by government for the purpose of addressing these threats of insecurity (Ogechi 2021). A cursory glance at the Nigerian daily newspapers will convince one of the states of insecurity in the country. Youth restiveness, kidnapping, bombing, arson, militancy, insurgency inter alia, have become the order of the day

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(Ogheneako, 2014). National growth, economic development and human capital development have all been hampered by this social problem. Robert McNamara, a onetime president of the World Bank, once observed that no country can develop under an environment of insecurity. Also, argued that peace and stability, are necessary condition for growth and development. In the Nigeria context, Mordi (2013) noted that the nation's growth and stability have been truncated by the on-going mayhem and destruction of lives and property in different parts of the country by the menace of Boko-Haram in the Northern states, the militants and kidnappers in the south-South; among others. Food production has been grossly affected and on the decline as farming and agricultural activities have been hampered, while oil exploration, exploitation and export have been negatively affected in the North and south-south, respectively (Omoroge, 2012). In all these cases of insecurity, youths are the prominent figure in the crusade of crime. Such youths either lack requisite education that render them jobless, unemployable, poor and disenchanting; or are educated and are still jobless. Poor youth find it difficult to resist temptation to commit crime, provided such will open way to meet their immediate needs. In other word, education and national security are inexorably linked together. Little wondered that strength, security and wellbeing of any society rest squarely on the quality of education.

Effective Security and Sustainable Economic Development in Nigeria

Effective security is a prerequisite for sustainable economic development. Effective security is one that endures and lasts, one that will not roll back or recede, even in the face of threatening reversal waves. It is a kind of development which can assure the security and protection of the environmental and its resources presently and subsequently (Ogechi 2021). When the security of any nation is threatened, the economic development of such is grossly affected. Sustainable development is an amalgam of two component words; namely "sustainable" and "development". A clearer understanding of each of these two component words is necessary to make this discourse more meaningful. The literary meaning of "sustainable" is that which can continue or be continued for a long time; capable of being maintained at a set level, keep up assumed role competently (The American Heritage Dictionary, 2000; The 21st Chambers Dictionary, 2001; Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, 2003; Hornby, 2005) in Ogechi, (2021). Establishing relationship between adult education and security for sustainable economic development, require peace and harmony to function. Sustainable security and economic development through education foster healthy and safe environment where people can thrive and function in a sustainable way. Viewed from this perspective, security is one of the most basic needs of people no matter the age bracket or status and also the territorial environment.

In Maslow's hierarchy of needs, security and safety is ranked second to physiological needs. This is a motivational theory in Psychology with a five-tier model of human needs. This theory assumed that lower needs in the hierarchy must be satisfied although not totally, before individuals can attend to higher needs. These needs are: physiological, safety, love and belonging, esteem and self-actualization. However, these needs have been further divided into two: deficiency needs and growth needs. Deficiency needs arise due to deprivation leading to insecurity and economic deprivation if not met. The most basic need of an individual is physical survival and this is what motivate and control human behaviour. Individuals' inability to satisfy deficiency needs causes insecurity, youth restlessness and other social vices rampaging the society most especially in Nigeria.

Modern day research in social sciences and education also requires that theoretical and rational foundation be provided for overall conceptualisation of critical phenomena and issues in the society for proper clarification. Hence, Moronkola (2006) in Ogunyinka, (2014) opined that a theory is a set of formulations designed to explain and predict facts and events that can be observed. Thus, for the purpose of this paper, Maslow's Theory of Hierarchy of Needs is adapted for clarity of purpose and to buttress the inability of the society to meet the basic human needs propounded by Maslow leading to restiveness, kidnapping, high rate of unemployment among the youths causing high rate of insecurity in Nigeria.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs :(Mcleod, 2018)

According to the theory, basic needs must be met by an individual before moving to the next level of needs. However, the inability of most of the youths to meet the physiological and safety needs in the society is causing the high rate of insecurity in the country. People want to experience order, peace predictability and be in control of their lives (Mcleod 2020). Therefore, security is also a political issue on account of the key decisions that need to be made by country's authorities to regard a particular issue as a priority. Ensuring security is regarded as one of the most fundamental objectives and functions of country. Generally, it depicts protection against military attacks, but it includes security from terrorism, economic security, food security, cyber security, and territorial/environmental security, maintenance of independence and sovereignty of the nation and security for natural disaster. Security becomes the core fulcrum on which revolves all other developmental indices of a state or nation. The economic, social, political and indeed every other dimension of development are all anchored on security.

In realization of this fact the Nigerian constitution regards security as the fundamental objective of state policy. It is also observable that the governments adopt some measures which include political, economic, military, civil, diplomacy, dialogue and other intelligent tactic to safeguard the security of the nation. In all, adult education provides the skills, needed information, education, debate forum, knowledge, sensitization and creativity to develop new approaches that are necessary for sustainable security and economic development. A paradigm shift is only possible through critical, conscious and innovative exposure of citizens to adult education that is more encompassing.

Causes of Insecurity in Nigeria

Ogheneakoke (2014) identified a plethora of factors as causes of insecurity in Nigeria. These include, but not limited to, the following: Corruption, Marginalization, Social inequality, Ethnicity, Poverty and greed, Loss of value system, Religious intolerance, Foreign infiltration – insurgency, Bad leadership, Youth unemployment, Porosity of our borders, Falling standard of education, Poor judiciary system, Cultism and cult activities, High value for material things, Manipulation of electoral processes by political parties, Lack of trust on security agents, and Human right abuses among other causes.

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Implication of Insecurity in Nigeria

The socio-political and economic landscape in Nigeria has been blighted by the endemic twin evil of crime and violence (Seji et al 2020). The abysmal failure of successive administrations in Nigeria to address challenges of poverty, unemployment and inequitable distribution of wealth among ethnic nationalities, ultimately resulted in anger, frustration, agitation and violent crimes against the Nigerian state by individuals and groups. Such crimes include militancy, kidnapping, bombing, armed robbery, destruction of government properties, among others. The activities of various militia groups consequently resulted in low income for government from oil revenue, moderating the gross domestic product growth (GDP) rate, low participation of local and foreign investors in economic development and insecurity of lives and properties of the citizens (Seji D.O. Omoroje, Philip Onyekachukwu Egbule, 2020).

The cost of life and material resources to insecurity in the country since the past few years is unquantifiable. According to Human Rights Watch, a security monitoring agency, between 2009 and 2012, about 2,000 lives had been lost to militia insurgency; within the first nine months in 2012, 815 people were killed in 275 suspected attacks, and more than 60 police stations were attacked in 10 Northern states, excluding the bombed police headquarters in Abuja. Tens of dozens are still nursing various degrees of injuries. The data base of orphans and widows caused by the rampaging sects has grown vastly, swelling the numbers of internally displaced persons (IDPS). Money from some international organization and funds raised locally from governmental, non-governmental agencies, charitable organizations and individuals that is supposed to be channeled to human capital development has been deployed for the rehabilitation of families of the casualties and the renovation of properties destroyed. Yearly, unspecified millions of naira is being paid as ransom for the release of victims of kidnappers: not forgetting the Central Bank of Nigeria's N100 million cash donation, N200 million donation from the combined efforts of the opposition governors, and the \$50,000 (USD) from the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN), America chapter, to reduce the suffering of the victims of regional militia (Seji et al 2020).

As Nigeria struggles with the army of unemployed youths of about 24%, companies in their numbers are closing down operations in Boko-Haram ravaged North and oil-rich South-South, and relocating to other African countries for loss of lives and properties (Seji et al 2020). And the few remaining companies operate on skeletal bases. Construction workers and expatriates providing specialized services on various projects in these regions have fled for safety. This development has multiplied the number of unemployed youths roaming the street which has become an easy tool for violence. This scenario has not only deepened the existing unemployment rate but also paints a gloomy picture of poverty. Education is the bedrock of social economic development (Freire, 1970). In Ogechi (2021) The Islamic militants have serially attacked students and facilities in educational institutions in different Northern states of the country (Chibok Girls and Burnin Yadin Boys Government Schools) (Seji et al 2020). Over time, a lot of schools have shut down their academic programmes as a result of insurgency, banditry and kidnapping. These have drastically impacted the teaming number of students seeking admission into academic institutions at all levels. For example, University of Maiduguri, one of the most affordable universities in Nigeria which is known for turning down admission of students because of quality and to avoid overcrowding of facility, now solicits for admission through different media outreach. Also recently, a respondent survey shows that many students have vowed never to participate in the compulsory one-year National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) programme if posted to the Northern part of the country (Seji et al 2020). Those who were inadvertently posted to the North redeployed immediately after three weeks of mandatory camping. This development therefore defeats the core mandate of setting up the Act of NYSC in 1973 (FinIntell, 2013).

Roles of Adult Education in Checkmating Insecurity in Nigeria

There is a significant relationship between National security and education, a cursory look at the personality of Boko-Haram Islamists and bandits in the Northern region of Nigeria reveals high level or rate of illiteracy among them (Seji et al 2020). It is in the light of this that the Emir of Kano, HRM Lamido Sanusi, admonished the elites of the region to establish schools, instead of building mosques. Also, in a bid to help reduce the rate of illiteracy the past administration of President Goodluck Jonathan established Nomadic education and Al-Manjeri schools in the Northern region. UNESCO (2008) stated that "No development can be possible without humans, and no humans can reach development without quality education". It is in light of this, that Anadi (2008) opined that for a nation to be developed and secured, there must be a very considerable proportion of trained educated citizens in that nation not only to act as doctors, engineers, teachers, agriculturist, scientists, and the likes, but also to create a new class sufficiently large and hence, sufficiently strong to establish its own values of justice, security, selection on merit, flexibility, empiricism and efficiency. For this to be actualized, the education system (primary, secondary and tertiary levels) must be practical and functional. Therefore, quality education is the primary agents of national

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security and development for bringing the vision of society into reality. “For example, if the militants, Boko-Haram, armed robbers and kidnapers were properly nurtured with quality formal, informal and indigenous education from the grass root level, all the security threats/challenges such as terrorism, riots/civil unrest, demonstrations, intolerance, cult-related criminal acts, religious intolerance, armed robbery, intra and inter-ethnic strife, drug trafficking, human trafficking, kidnapping, hijacks and many other vices threatening lives and properties would not have been in existence” (Osakwe, 2013).

However, in order to make adult education a tool for achieving effective security and sustainable economic development in Nigeria, the following suggestions are made:

1. Adequate allocation should be made for education in the National budget to meet the UNESCO International benchmark of 26 percent to make more funds available for education and ultimately for adult education.
Adult education practice should be reviewed constantly, organized and systematized in order to develop a more coherent and useful agenda for adult education to give it the needed respect among other disciplines.
2. There should be more awareness through mobilization and advocacy because many interested learners are not aware of the existence of adult education centres and even the programmes, they are supposed to enroll in.
3. There should be establishment of more centres of adult education in the six geo-political areas of the country so that every individual will have easy access to education and not have need to travel long distances to acquire skills and knowledge needed for security and development.
4. Basic and Post literacy programmes should be free in all the states of the Federation and the programmes should be based on the learners’ needs and aspirations.
5. Upward review of facilitators’ remuneration should be in accordance with the minimum benchmark as set by the Non-Formal Education blue print that facilitators should be paid minimum wage as their remuneration or allowances.
6. Only qualified persons with Nigeria Certificate in Education and specialization in adult education should be employed as facilitators in the Non-Formal Education centres.
More capacity building programmes (pre-service, in-service and on-the-job training) for Adult and Non- Formal Education personnel at all levels should be put in place.
7. There should be regular and effective monitoring of programmes at all levels and there should be capacity building for monitoring and evaluation of officers through short-, medium- and long-term training programmes, workshops, conferences amongst others.
8. People will have good perception of adult education programmes, if they are timely, relevant and innovative and if these programmes reflect practical and real-life situation. The negative perception will change to positive one, when there is effective management and administration of adult education programmes.
9. The introduction of peace education as an integral part of the adult at this critical period of Nigeria's nation-hood is quite imperative and if properly designed and developed, it will help to control the rising cases of insecurity and armed conflicts in some parts of Nigeria.

Conclusion

Adult education being life-long and life wide learning activities provide programmes that address any particular issue. With peace education sustainable development is achievable which invariably will lead to economic development. The goal of peace education is to curb violence by resolving conflicts in a non-violent manner to share limited resources equitably and live within the limits of sustainability. When people develop sound mind and right sound attitude, there will be harmony tranquility, peace, accord and acceptability without fear. Farmers can go to farm, fisher men to rivers, traders to markets, students go to school without fear, workers work and come back home, free movement and transportation of goods and services, value of life is restored and economic is invariably developed.

Recommendations

1. This paper therefore suggests that a revitalized adult education is a tool that could be used in achieving human capacity for sustainable security and economic development in Nigeria.
2. Through Adult Education programmes, the much needed technical and vocational knowledge, skills, values and attitudes needed by the adult populace for sustainable development are achieved. In addition, also, adult education will enable people to become well-informed, capable of thinking critically and owning their destiny through active participation.
3. Successful and sustainable development cannot be achieved when majority of the populace is illiterate.

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4. Thus, the political will to encourage adult education especially in areas of funding would only be achieved through a deliberate and sustained effort by government to ensure that the percentage of fund allocated to education in the yearly national budgets meet the international bench-mark of 15-25 per cent as recommended by UNESCO in 2018 among several other measures discussed to revitalize Adult Education.

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